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MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI FANINI OLIY TA'LIM TALABALARIGA O'QITISHDAGI QO'YILGAN ASOSIY TALABLAR

Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o'g'li

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti, 1-bosqich magistrant.

maqsudu32@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560887>

ANNOTATSIYA

Axborot texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish jarayoni hayotimizning barcha sohalariga ta'sir qiladi. Ta'lim tizimi bundan mustasno emas. O'quv jarayonida qo'llaniladigan an'anaviy yondashuvlar kompyuter texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi va aloqa texnologiyalarini, shu jumladan Internet texnologiyalarini takomillashtirish ta'siri ostida o'zgarib bormoqda. Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining turli sohalariga interfaol va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini faol joriy etish tobora murakkablashmoqda.

Ma'lumotlar bazasi fanini o'qitishda ham axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish kerakli natijalarni berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ma'lumotlar bazasi, SQL, AKT, interfaol, innovatsion, ma'lumotlar bazasini boshqarish tizimlari.

ANNOTATION

The process of developing information technology affects all spheres of our lives. The educational system is no exception. The traditional approaches used in the educational process are changing under the influence of the rapid development of computer technology and the improvement of communication technologies, including Internet technologies. The active introduction of interactive and information and communication technologies into various spheres of the modern educational system is becoming more complicated.

Even in the teaching of database Science, the use of information and communication technology has yielded the desired results.

Keywords: database, SQL, ICT, interactive, innovative, database management systems.

KIRISH

Zamonaviy sharoitda o'qitishdagi innovatsiyalarni ta'limda qo'llaniladigan pedagogik texnologiyalar, texnikalar va vositalarni rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish

jarayoni sifatida tavsiflash mumkin. Bizning fikrimizcha, innovatsion pedagogik faoliyatni ta'lim faoliyatining asosiy tarkibiy qismlaridan biri va ta'lim muassasalari muvaffaqiyatining muhim ko'rsatkichi sifatida ko'rib chiqish kerak.

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ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI

Ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish va ulardan foydalanish davlatning raqobatdoshligi, shuningdek, uning jahon maydoniga integratsiyasini kengaytirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish zamonaviy o'quv jarayonini amalga oshirishning zaruriy shartlaridan biridir, chunki bu sifat jihatidan yangi axborot ta'lim muhitini yaratish uchun imkoniyat yaratadi. Ta'kidlash joizki, oliy o'quv yurtlarida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan (AKT) foydalanish yurtimizning oliy ta'limi sifati va ochiqligini ta'minlashda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Mavjud pedagogik amaliyotni tahlil qilib, biz ta'limdagi innovatsiyalarni quyidagicha ajratib ko'rsatishimiz mumkin: ma'lumotlarning gipermatnli taqdimoti;

interfaol jihozlardan, shu jumladan elektron doskalardan foydalanish; prezentatsiyalarni yaratish va taqdim etish; masofaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish; videokonferensiya texnologiyasidan foydalanish; interfaol o'quv majmualarini rivojlantirish.

"Ma'lumotlar bazasi" fanini o'qitishdagi axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish quyidagi natijalar olib keladi:

birinchidan, fanni o'qitishda AKTni joriy etish bilimlarni to'plash va ijtimoiy tajribani to'plashni sezilarli darajada tezlashtiradi. Misol tariqasida, an'anaviy ma'ruza mashg'ulotlarida talabalarga katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni o'rganish talab qilinganda, ma'lumotlarni oddiy doskalarga yozish yoki so'zlab berish anchagina vaqtni ta'lab qiladi. Agar mashg'ulotni elektron doskalar va ko'rgazmali materiallar orqali o'tkazilsa, talabalarga qiziqarli va yangi ma'lumotlarni o'zlashtirish oson kichadi.

ikkinchidan, materialni takrorlash va o'rganishdagi vaqtni tejaydi; uchinchidan, zamonaviy AKT ta'lim va ta'lim sifatini yaxshilaydi, bu insonga atrof-muhit va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarga muvaffaqiyatli va tez moslashishga imkon beradi, shuningdek har bir kishiga zarur bilimlarni olish imkoniyatini beradi;

to'rtinchidan, ta'limga AKTni faol va samarali joriy etish davlat ta'lim standarti talablariga javob beradigan, zamonaviy jamiyat talablari sharoitida ta'lim tizimini isloh qilish jarayonini yaratishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

NATIJALAR

Biz AKTdan foydalangan holda darslarni o'tkazish an'anaviy usullardan ancha farq qilishiga e'tibor qaratamiz:

birinchidan, o'qituvchidan maxsus mahorat, o'qitish usullari talab etiladi, yani pedagog IKT dan xabardor bo'lishi, o'z ustida ishlashi va tajribasini oshirishi zarur;

ikkinchidan, zamonaviy kompyuterga yo'naltirilgan darsning o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, diqqat markazida asta-sekin uning o'quv jarayonini faol qurayotgan o'quvchiga yo'naltiriladi. Masalan "Ma'lumotlar bazasi" fanining laboratoriya darsida "SQL" so'rovlar tilini o'rganish bo'yicha mashg'ulotlar o'tkaziladi. Mashg'ulotlardagi dasturlarni o'qituvchi to'g'rida to'g'ri talabalarga proyektor orqali tuzib, natijalarni olib ko'rsatsa, ularda qiziqish va darsni o'zlashtirish yuqori bo'ladi. Bu o'z navbatida pedagogdan chuqur bilim va tajriba talab qiladi, zero bitta hato unga bo'lgan ishonchni kamaytiradi.

MUHOKAMA

Mashg'ulotga innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llashda zamonaviy o'qituvchining vazifalari:

- butun dars davomida (ma'ruza) talabaning bilim faolligini qo'llab-quvvatlash;
- uning axborot maydoniga muvaffaqiyatli o'tishiga ko'maklashish;
- turli xil ma'lumotlarni o'zlashtirish muammolarini hal qilishda yordam berish.

Ma'lumki, boshlang'ich bilimlarni egallashga qaratilgan o'quv faoliyatining asosiy turi - bu ma'ruza. Uning asosiy maqsadi o'qitishning nazariy asoslarini yaratish, o'quv faoliyati va aniq akademik intizomga bo'lgan qiziqishni rivojlantirish, mustaqil ishlash bo'yicha talabalarning ko'rsatmalarini shakllantirishdir. An'anaviy ma'ruza nafaqat ma'lumotni uzatish usuli sifatida, balki o'qituvchilarning talabalarga hissiy ta'sir ko'rsatish usuli sifatida ham, ularning faolligini oshiradigan shubhasiz afzalliklarga ega. Axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish an'anaviy ma'ruzalar, seminarlar va mahorat darslarida ishlatiladigan o'quv materiallarini uzatish usullarini o'zgartirishga imkon beradi. O'qituvchi laboratoriya mavzulariga muvofiq o'zlarining elektron manbalarini yaratishi va ularni talabalarga tanishtirish uchun taklif qilishi mumkin. O'z navbatida, dars davomida Internet manbalariga kirish zarur ma'lumotlarni tezda qidirish qobiliyatini ta'minlaydi, talabalar ishini faollashtiradi, ularni muammoni muhokama qilishda, munozarada ishtirok etishga undaydi.

O'quv jarayonida foydalaniladigan axborot texnologiyalarining tarkibiy qismlaridan biri bu videofilmlarni namoyish etishdir. Video filmlarga taqdimotning bir qismi yoki elektron qo'llanma sifatida yoki yangi materialni namoyish qilishda mustaqil element sifatida qarashimiz mumkin. Masalan, "Ma'lumotlar bazasi" fani laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini video yozuv shaklida

saqlab, talabalarga taqdim etilsa, talabalar ushbu materialni to'liq yodlashga va takrorashga yordam beradi. Ushbu bosqichda ta'limga bo'lgan qiziqish va sifatni sezilarli darajada oshadi.

XULOSA

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, oliy talimni axborotlashtirishning asosiy vazifasi talabalarga oliy ma'lumot olishlari, malaka oshirishlari, intellektual salohiyatlarini o'quv jarayoniga innovatsion axborot-kommunikatsiya va ta'lim texnologiyalarini joriy etishlari uchun qulay sharoitlar yaratishdan iborat. Mavjud va kelajakdagi innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar va usullar innovatsion axborot texnologiyalaridan, birinchi navbatda kompyuter va telekommunikatsiyalardan keng foydalanilmasdan amalga oshirilmaydi, chunki ular yordamida ushbu texnologiyalar va usullarning didaktik funksiyalarini to'liq ochib berish va ulardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini anglash mumkin.

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